

The Relationship between a Teachers Perception of Organizational Identity and Work Effort

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Abstract

The purpose of this research is to determine the relationship between a teachers' perception of organizational identity and work effort. The study sample group consists of 392 teachers working in public and private schools in Başakşehir, Istanbul in the 2020-2021 academic year. In order to collect data in the research, the "Teacher Organizational Identity Perception Scale" developed by Tabak and Boyacı (2019) and the "Work Effort Scale" adapted into Turkish by Özdemir, A. (2013) were used. In this study, which was carried out using the relational screening method within the scope of the quantitative research method, the data was collected with a questionnaire consisting of three parts consisting of 22 questions. The collected data were analyzed with the SPSS 21 program. Since the data did not show normal distribution, the Mann Whitney U Test and the Kruskal Wallis Test, which are nonparametric tests were used in the analysis of the data. As a result of the research, it was determined that the teachers' organizational identity perceptions and work effort were at a high level. The difference in the communication sub-dimension between the teachers' perceptions of organizational identity and the level of education variable was found to be statistically significant. However, there was no statistically significant difference in the teachers' perceptions of organizational identity and work effort according to gender, years of seniority, educational status and type of institution. In addition, it was determined that teachers' organizational identity perceptions positively affected their work effort.

Keywords: Work Effort, Identity, Teacher, Perception of Organizational Identity

Introduction

In recent years, there has been an increase in the researches made with the increasing interest in the subject of organizational identity. Investigations have been made at many levels in the organizational field. These levels include the subject of studies at an individual level expressing the sense of self in the organization, the group level, the identity formed by the organization as a whole, the organizational level, the cultural level formed by the interaction of the organization with other organizations and society (Cornelissen et al., 2007). In this study, the effect of organizational identity on employees work effort was investigated.

The study shows that the individual is different from others with his/her personal attitudes and behaviors such as knowledge, skills, interests and abilities (Yıldız,2013). The individual's identity and the individual's own behavior affect both the individual and the group's behavior. The identity of the organization affects the behavior of the organization. In studies conducted in this area, individual identity researchers ask "Who am I?" While seeking an answer to the question, organizational identity researchers ask "who are we?" and seeks an answer to the question (Elsbach and Kramer,1996). While organizational identity is being formed, "who are we?", "what do we do?", "how do we do it?" answers to questions are sought. The answers to these questions are very important for successful organizational identity formation (Sethi and Compau,2002).

Organizational identity is the perception that organizations' attitudes, behaviors, practices, philosophy and visual (emblem, logo, color, etc.) elements create on employees and people (Korkmaz,2007Cobanoglu, 2008). These perceptions are very important. Positive perceptions increase the individual's performance and effort (Tutar&Altnoz,2010). Attitudes and practices of the organization such as a comfortable communication environment within the organization, feedbacks that can be received from colleagues, realistic discussion, determination of goals and objectives, and regular meetings will increase individual and organizational performance. The manager also has a role in the formation of positive perceptions. Behaviors such as inspiring, reliable, active, effective communicator and knowledge of the leader will also bring positive attitudes and practices. Both the environment of the organization and the characteristics of the leader are the most important issues that will affect the perception of organizational identity (Gulsen,2010; Akgul,2012).

The three points that organizational identity reflects are belonging (sharing of common goals), support (supportive attitudes and behaviors of the organization), communication (between the employees of the organization). These three points and the effort to work are extremely important in the organization (Tabak and Boyacı,2019). Studies to determine the reasons that increase teachers' sincere commitment and effort to their schools or prevent them from showing effort have gained importance in recent years (George and Bettenhouse,1990). In recent years, researchers have realized that these behaviors can be better understood by determining their relationship with organizational characteristics (Dipaola, Hoy,2005).

Effort to work means extra work and concentration on work. The first of these is the work done by an employee in a way that exceeds the normal working time, and the second is the work performed in a unit time. In other words, it shows high performance in the current working time (Avgoustaki, Frankort,2019: 637). Due to the increasing need for teachers in the development of schools in recent years, both school principals and senior administrators expect teachers to be diligent in their work. The positive organizational identity that will be formed by the belonging of the teachers to their institutions, the communication with their colleagues and the support of the organization on the teacher will affect the work effort of the teacher.

In the 2023 National Education Vision Document, the following statements were made while talking about the impact of the teacher on the education system: "The success of all kinds of reform and improvement efforts in the education system, especially in education policies, in areas such as curriculum, materials and technology, largely depends on the professional competencies, perceptions and dedication of teachers and school administrators(MEB, 2018, p.40). This emphasizes the importance of the perception and effort of the teacher's corporate identity in the education system.

Organizational Identity

The individual identity, which begins to form in the first years of an individual's childhood, continues to develop positively or negatively throughout life. Every individual around us has a unique identity. Individual identity laid the foundation for the association of the concept of identity with the organization. It is a very difficult process to provide a direct transition to organizational identity. From a broad perspective, the differentiation of classical organizational forms has increased the interest in organizational identity to create structures and methods specific to the organizations' institutions (Tüzün, 2008; Gioia, 1998).

In today's increasingly competitive environment, institutions and organizations themselves want to stand out from their competitors. For this reason, the corporate identity they will create is of great importance. Organizational identity is built by considering the vision of the institution or the organization, its adopted attitudes and attitudes as a whole (Çeken, 2016). It is defined by the organizational identity of an institution. Organizational subunits or subsystems "How does it behave?", "What does it say?", "What does it do, what does it sell?" Questions are the parts that make up the whole. In other words, it creates a very close relationship between the physical structure, functioning, units and employees that make up the organization and the organizational identity (Hepkon, 2003). "Organizational identity is also expressed as the metaphors people use when describing the organization, the way an organization is recognized, the image that the organization rouses in their minds and the effect it rouses in people." Organizational identity is among the most important factors that define the organization and keep the employees together (Akatay, 2008:302).

Work Effort

Individuals who are diligent in both business and personal life are excited and enthusiastic. These feelings that occur in people bring with them the instinct to produce new things and create works. As a matter of fact, the performance of diligent individuals will be different from the performance of otherwise reluctant individuals. When we look at the universe, every being is in labor and effort. Since the human being is the creature with the highest expectation in the universe, the duty of the human being is to put effort and effort. Many of the problems faced by the individual are due to not showing enough effort. Of course, the effort to be made here should not be random, but planned and programmed (Erel, 2012).

The word effort, according to TDK, means "continuous work, toil, desire to work to achieve something" (TDK, 2021). Work effort is defined as "the power, energy or activity by which work is performed" (Brown and Peterson, 1994: 71). Effort also means concentration on work and making extra effort. It is the work done by the employee exceeding the normal working time and secondly, the work performed in the unit time. It is the situation of increasing the performance according to the unit time (Avgoustaki and Frankort, 2019: 637).

Purpose and Importance

The increase in success in schools is possible with the belonging of teachers to their institutions and the subsequent effort they will show. This study is important in terms of determining the effect of teachers' organizational identity perceptions on their performance and hard work. When the literature was scanned, it was observed that there were not enough studies on teachers' work effort. It will contribute to the literature in terms of addressing this deficiency. This research is also important in terms of providing important information to education administrators and school administrators, gaining new perspectives and serving education.

In line with the explanations made and the importance of the research, the general purpose of the research was established. The general purpose of the study is to determine the relationship between teachers' perceptions of organizational identity and work effort. In line with this general purpose, answers to the following questions were sought.

1. What is the teachers' perception of organizational identity?
2. At the level of teachers' perception of organizational identity; Is there a significant difference according to gender, years of seniority, education level, level of education, type of institution?
3. What is the level of teachers' work effort?
4. At the level of teachers' work effort; Is there a significant difference according to gender, years of seniority, education level, level of education, type of institution?
5. What is the effect of teachers' organizational identity perceptions of work effort?

Method

This research, which was conducted with the aim of determining the relationship between teachers' perceptions of organizational identity and their work efforts, was planned and conducted in accordance with the general survey model and relational survey method within the scope of quantitative research techniques. According to (Karasar,2005), general survey models are survey arrangements made over the whole of the universe or a group, samples or samples to be taken from the universe in order to make a general judgment about the universe consisting of many elements. The relational screening method to be applied aims to determine the existence or degree of covariance between two or more variables (Karasar,2005).

Findings

Working group

The universe group of the research consists of 6291 teachers working in the public and private schools of the Ministry of National Education in the Başakşehir district of Istanbul in the 2020-2021 academic year.

The study group of this research consisted of 392 teachers who voluntarily participated in the study in the public and private schools affiliated to the Ministry of National Education in the Başakşehir District of Istanbul in the 2020-2021 academic year. Teachers from the schools affiliated to the district were randomly selected. Statistical operations were performed on a total of 392 questionnaires.

When the demographic information of 392 teachers participating in the research was examined; 38.8% of the teachers were male and 61.2% were female. When the seniority of the teachers in the sample group were examined, 27% of the teachers were between 0-5 years, 34.2% were between 6-10 years, 19.6% were between 11-15 years, 6.6% were between 16-20 years. It is seen that 7.1% of them continue their teaching profession for 21-25 years and 5.4% of them for 26 years or more. It is seen that 80.9% of the teachers in the sample group obtained a Bachelors Degree and 19.1% were Master Degree holders. Considering the educational institution levels of the teachers, it is seen that 5.4% of the teachers participating in the research work at preschool, 36% at primary school, 32.7% at secondary school and 26% at high school. It was determined that 92.6% of the teachers in the sample group were working in public institutions, while 7.4% were working in private institutions.

Data Collection Tools

In order to collect the data in the research, the "Teacher Organizational Identity Perception Scale" developed by Tabak and Boyacı (2019) and the "Work Effort Scale" adapted into Turkish by Özdemir, A. (2013) were used. For both questionnaires, permission to use was obtained from the relevant researcher.

Teacher Organizational Identity Perception Scale

The "Teacher Organizational Identity Perception Scale" developed by Tabak & Boyacı (2019) were used to determine teachers' perceptions of organizational identity. The Teachers' Perception of Organizational Identity Scale consists of a total of 17 items and 3 factors. "Support (8 Items)", "Belonging (4 Items)" and the last factor is "Communication (5 Items)". Participants showed how much they agreed or disagreed with each item on a five-point Likert-type scale according to the scales of 1 = Strongly disagree and 5 = Strongly agree. In this study, it was found that the Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Coefficient of support subdimension was .925, sub-dimension of belonging was .754, and communication sub-dimension was .797. It is seen that the overall Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Coefficient of the scale is .914. Confirmatory factor analysis was performed to test the validity of the scale. When the confirmatory factor analysis findings of the scale of teachers' perceptions of organizational identity were examined, it was seen that the factor load values of the scale items ranged between .41 and .94. When the factor load value is .30 and above, it is at an acceptable level (Büyüköztürk, 2002). According to Kalaycı, (2008), when the KMO value is greater than .60, it is understood that the factor analysis of the sample size is sufficient. As a result of the test for factor analysis of the sample size, KMO= .874, it is at an acceptable level.

Work Effort Scale

In order to measure the efforts of teachers in their professional lives, the "Work Effort Scale" prepared by Kuvaas and Dysvik (2009) and translated into Turkish by Özdemir, A. (2013) were adapted. The scale consists of 5 items. Participants showed how much they agreed or disagreed with each item on a five-point Likert-type scale according to the scales of 1 = Strongly disagree, 5 = Strongly agree. In this study, the Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient of the work effort scale was found to be .791. When the confirmatory factor analysis findings of the Organizational Work Effort scale were examined, it was seen that the factor load values of the scale items were distributed between .40 and .57. As a result of the test for factor analysis of the sample size, KMO= .664, it is at an acceptable level. According to Kilic (2016), who states that there are different classifications in the literature regarding Cronbach's alpha value, the widely accepted classification is as follows: ≥ 0.9 excellent, $0.7 \leq \alpha < 0.9$ good, $0.6 \leq \alpha < 0.7$ acceptable, $0.5 \leq \alpha < 0.6$ weak, $\alpha < 0.5$ is unacceptable. According to this classification, internal consistency coefficients of teacher organizational identity perception scale and work effort scale were found to be at a good level.

Data Collection

The data related to the research were collected with a three-part questionnaire consisting of 22 questions. In the first part, there are questions to determine the demographic characteristics of the researched people, in the second part, there are questions to determine the organizational identity perceptions of the participants in the research, and in the third part, the questions determine the work efforts of the teachers participating in the research. The data was

collected online through Google Forms from teachers working in Istanbul's Basaksehir district.

Analysis of Data

The data related to the research were collected through a questionnaire and entered into the SPSS 21 program. It was examined whether there were erroneous or missing data. Before starting the analysis of the obtained data, it was checked whether the data showed a normal distribution. In order to determine the normality of the data, the Shapiro Wilks Test is applied if the number of data is less than 30, and the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (Lilliefors) Test is applied if it is more than 30 (Kalaycı,2008). Since the number of teachers participating in the study was 392, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (Lilliefors) Test was applied and the significance value for both scales was found to be less than .05. Distorted and kurtosis values were checked to ensure that the data were not normally distributed. When the distortions and kurtosis values are ± 1.5 , the data are considered to have a normal distribution. (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2013). As a result of the normality test, the distort value for the teachers' perceptions of organizational identity scale was 3.10 and the kurtosis value was 3.14, the distort value for the work effort scale was 2.54 and the kurtosis value was 0. Therefore, it can be said that the scores of the teachers' perceptions of organizational identity scale and the work effort scale do not comply with the normal distribution. Therefore, Mann Whitney U Test and Kruskal Wallis Test, which are non-parametric tests, were used in the analysis of the data obtained from this study. Significance was tested at the 0.05 level for the Mann Whitney U Test and the Kruskal Wallis Test. Bonferroni correction was made to prevent the type I error that could interfere with the measurement process in the Mann Whitney U

Test, which was used to determine between which pairs the significant differences obtained in the Kruskal Wallis Test were. Frequency and percentage calculations were made to determine the demographic information of the teachers participating in the research. The arithmetic mean and standard deviation were calculated to determine the teachers' level of organizational identity perception and work effort. The Mann Whitney U Test was used to compare the teachers' organizational identity perception level and work effort level according to gender, educational status and the institution they are affiliated with. Kruskal Wallis Test was used to compare according to the variable of seniority and education level. Spearman's Correlation Coefficient was calculated to determine the effect of teachers' organizational identity perception level on work effort.

Results, Conclusions and Recommendations

In the study, the arithmetic mean and standard deviation values of the answers given to the questionnaire questions were calculated in order to determine the level of organizational identity perceptions of the teachers in the sample group, and the results are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Organizational Identity Perception Level of Teachers (N=392)

	Dimension Variables	□	SS	Participation Level
Support	1. My school supports my professional development.	3,80	1,051	Agree
	2. I can adequately demonstrate my potential at school.	3,70	,973	Agree
	3. I know that my school will support me when I encounter a problem.	3,51	1,169	Agree
	4. I know that my school will protect my rights in the implementation of laws and regulations.	3,77	1,169	Agree
	5. When I start a study, I feel the support of my school.	3,71	1,145	Agree
	6. My school appreciates the work of teachers.	3,67	1,098	Agree
	7. The goals of my school and what I want to do overlap.	3,68	1,183	Agree
	8. My school is committed to its institutional values.	4,08	,987	Strongly Agree
Belonging	9. I see the problems of my school as my own problems.	3,84	,977	Agree
	10. I make an effort beyond what is expected to make my school successful.	4,04	,936	Strongly Agree
	11. I will teach even if I don't need money.	3,41	1,189	Agree
	12. I use the phrase we when talking about my school.	4,20	1,034	Strongly Agree
Communication	13. When I have a problem, I can share it with my colleagues at my school.	3,87	1,003	Agree
	14. There is a positive communication environment in my school.	3,66	1,056	Agree
	15. I tell my colleagues at my school about my projects.	3,98	,920	Agree
	16. Communication among the staff at my school is strong.	3,84	,839	Agree
	17. When I start a study, I know that I will receive the necessary support from other teachers.	3,82	1,032	Agree

When Table 1 is examined, the average of the proposition ($=3.51$) that the 392 teachers participated in the research regarding the organizational identity perception level is the least, "I will teach even if I don't need money." It is seen that they have a proposition and they express an opinion as "I agree". The proposition with which the teachers agreed the most was ($=4.20$), with an average of "I use the expression we are when talking about my school." It is seen that they have a proposition and they express an opinion as "I totally agree".

Apart from that, the teachers said, "My school supports me in my professional development." proposition "I agree" with an average of ($=3.80$), "I can demonstrate my potential sufficiently at my school." proposition ($=3.70$) with an average of "I agree", "I can show my potential sufficiently at my school." proposition ($=3.70$) with an average of "I agree", "I know that my school will support me when I encounter a problem." with an average of ($=3.51$), "I agree", "I know that my school will protect my rights in the implementation of laws and regulations." proposition ($=3.77$) with an average of "I agree", "I feel the support of my school when I start a study." proposition ($=3.71$) with the mean "I agree", "The goals of my school and what I want to do overlap." proposition ($=3.68$) with an average of "I agree", "My school is committed to its institutional values." ($=4.08$) with an average of "I strongly agree", "I see the problems of my school as my own problems" ($=3.84$) with an average of "I agree", "I make an effort beyond the expected for my school to be successful." proposition ($=4.04$) with an average of

“Strongly Agree”, “When I have a problem, I can share it with my colleagues at my school.” (=3.87) with an average of “I agree”, “There is a positive communication environment in my school.” proposition (=3.66) with an average of “I agree”, “I tell my colleagues at my school about my projects.” proposition (=3.98) with an average of “I agree”, “Communication is strong among the staff at my school.” proposition (=3.84) with an average of “I agree”, “I know that I will get the necessary support from other teachers when I start a study.” It is seen that the proposition ((=3.82) is at the level of “I agree” with the mean.

It is seen that the general average of teachers' organizational identity perception level is at the level of "I agree" with (=3.79).

As a result of the Mann Whitney U Test, which was conducted to determine whether there is a difference according to gender in the level of organizational identity perception of the teachers participating in the research, it was determined that there was no statistically significant difference between the levels of teachers' organizational identity perception and the sub-dimensions of the scale in terms of gender variable. . Support sub-dimension p= .744, belonging sub-dimension p= .788, and communication sub-dimension p= .373.

As a result of the Kruskal-Wallis Test, which was conducted to determine whether there is a difference in the level of seniority of the teachers participating in the research according to their years of seniority, there was no statistically significant difference at the 0.05 significance level between the organizational identity perceptions of the teachers in the sample group and the professional seniority variable ($X^2= 5.716$; $p=.335$).

As a result of the Mann Whitney U Test, which was conducted to determine whether there is a difference in the level of organizational identity perception of the teachers participating in the research according to their educational status, there was no statistically significant difference at 0.05 significance level between the organizational identity perceptions of the teachers in the sample group and the educational status variable of the scale. Support sub-dimension p= .459, belonging sub-dimension p= .784 communication sub-dimension p= .201. The Kruskal-Wallis Test was conducted in order to determine whether here is a difference in the level of organizational identity perception of the teachers participating in the research according to the educational level they work, and the result is given in Table 2.

Table 2. Kruskal-Wallis Test Analysis According to the Education Level Variable of Teachers' Perception of Organizational Identity

Lower Dimension	Education Level	N	Rank Average	X ²	p	Difference
Support	Pre-School	21	227,67	2,066	,559	None
	Primary School	141	190,94			
	Secondary School	128	199,38			
	High School	102	194,15			
Belonging	Pre-School	21	255,98	6,358	,095	None
	Primary School	141	191,11			
	Secondary School	128	196,24			
	High School	102	192,03			
Communication	Pre-School	21	270,07	10,032	,018*	Available
	Primary School	141	196,76			
	Secondary School	128	192,88			
	High School	102	185,54			

*p<0.05

When Table 2 is examined, as a result of the Kruskal-Wallis Test, no significant difference was found between the organizational identity perceptions of the teachers in the sample group and the variable of the level of education they work in, with the sub-dimensions of support and belonging. A significant relationship was found between the communication sub-dimension of the scale and the education level of the teachers ($p=0.018$). Mann Whitney U Test was applied to determine which groups caused this difference. According to the results of the analysis, between the teachers working at the preschool level and primary school teachers ($p=0.005$), between the teachers working at the pre-school level and the teachers working at the secondary school level ($p=0.004$), and between the teachers working at the pre-school level and the teachers working at the high school level ($p=0.005$). $p=0.002$) a significant difference was found. Accordingly, preschool teachers have higher communication perceptions than teachers working at primary, secondary and high school levels.

As a result of the Mann-Whitney U Test, which was conducted to determine whether there is a difference in the level of organizational identity perception of the teachers participating in the research according to the institution they are affiliated with, it was determined that there was no statistically significant difference between the organizational identity perception levels of the teachers and the subdimensions of the scale in terms of the institution they were affiliated with. Support sub-dimension $p= .900$, belonging sub-dimension $p= .992$, and communication sub-dimension $p= .260$.

In order to determine the work effort levels of the teachers participating in the research, the arithmetic mean and standard deviation values of the answers to the survey questions were calculated and the results are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Level of Work Effort of Teachers (N=392)

Variables	□	SS	Participation Level
1. I usually don't hesitate to make extra effort when needed.	4,13	,795	Absolutely Agree
2. I often put extra effort in doing my work.	4,03	,778	Absolutely Agree
3. When I am busy at school, I try very hard.	4,01	,819	Absolutely Agree
4. I try to work as hard as possible.	3,50	,996	Agree
5. I willingly show great effort while doing my job.	4,12	,777	Absolutely Agree

When Table 3 is examined, the average of the proposition ($=3.50$) that the teachers participating in the research showed the least participation regarding the level of work effort was “I try to work as hard as possible. ” and they expressed an opinion as “I agree”. It is seen that the teachers agreed with the proposition the most ($13=4.13$) with an average of “I totally agree”. Apart from that, the teachers who participated in the research said, “I usually make extra effort while doing my work.” proposition ($=4.03$) with an average of “Strongly Agree”, “I put a lot of effort when I have a busy job at school.” proposition ($=4.01$) with an average of “Strongly Agree”, “I willingly show great effort while doing my job.” ($=4.12$) with the mean as “I totally agree”.

The general average of the opinions of the teachers about the level of work effort is ($=3.95$) and “I agree”.

As a result of the Mann-Whitney U Test, which was conducted to determine whether there is a difference in the level of work effort of the teachers participating in the research according to gender, it was determined that there was no statistically significant difference between the levels of work effort of the teachers and the sub-dimensions of the scale in terms of the gender variable ($p= .265$).

As a result of the Kruskal-Wallis Test, which was conducted to determine whether there is a difference in the level of work effort of the teachers participating in the research according to the seniority year, there was no statistically significant difference at the 0.05 significance level between the professional seniority variable of the work effort level of the teachers in the sample group ($X^2= 10,356$; $p = .066$).

As a result of the Mann Whitney U Test, which was conducted to determine whether there is a difference in the level of work effort of the teachers participating in the research according to their educational status, there was no statistically significant difference at the 0.05 significance level between the sub-dimensions of the scale between the level of work effort of the teachers in the sample group and the educational status variable ($p = .389$).

As a result of the Kruskal-Wallis Test, which was conducted to determine whether there is a difference in the level of work effort of the teachers participating in the research according to the level of education they work, there was no significant difference between the level of work effort of the teachers in the sample group and the variable of education level ($X^2 = .987$; $p = .804$).

As a result of the Mann-Whitney U Test, which was conducted to determine whether there is a difference in the level of work effort of the teachers participating in the research according to the institution they belong to, it was determined that there was no statistically significant difference between the sub-dimensions of the scale in terms of the level of work effort of the teachers in terms of the institution they were affiliated with ($p = .817$).

In order to determine the effects of the organizational identity perceptions of the teachers participating in the research on their work effort, Spearman's Correlation Analysis was performed and the results are given in Table 4.

Table 4. Spearman's Correlation Analysis for the Effect of Teachers' Perceptions of Organizational Identity on Work Effort

Variables	Work Effort		
	r	p	r ²
Teachers' Perception of Organizational Identity	,339**	,000	,119

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

When Table 4 is examined, as a result of Spearman's Correlation Analysis, it has been determined that the teachers' perception of organizational identity has a positive and significant relationship with their work effort ($r = .339$; $p < .01$). Accordingly, it can be said that as teachers' organizational identity perceptions increase, their work effort will also increase. In addition, considering the coefficient of determination ($r^2 = .119$), it can be said that 11.9% of teachers' perceptions of organizational identity stem from work effort. It can be said that the remaining approximately 88% level is related to other variables.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In this study, which was conducted with the aim of determining the relationship between teachers' perceptions of organizational identity and their work efforts, teachers' organizational identity perception levels were found to be high with $\bar{x} = 3.79$ as "I Agree". In similar studies, Sanli and Arabaci (2016) and Erturk (2018) found that teachers' perceptions of organizational identity were high, while Cobanoğlu (2008), Tasdan (2015) and Yaykiran (2020) found that teachers' perceptions of organizational identity were moderate. Many researchers (Albert & Whetten, 1985; Dutton & Dukerich, 1991; Whetten, Lewis & Mischel, 1992) stated that employees with a high perception of organizational identity have more ownership of the organization and show more effort for the goals of the organization.

It was determined that there was no significant difference between the organizational identity perceptions of the teachers participating in the research and the gender variable. Gul (2015), in her study on "Examination of Teachers' Perceptions of Organizational Identity According to Demographic Variables", stated that female teachers' organizational identification levels are higher than male teachers. On the other hand, Akgül (2012), Şanlı and Arabacı (2016), Taşdan (2015) and Ertürk (2018) stated in their studies that male teachers' perceptions of organizational identity are higher than female teachers.

It was determined that there was no significant difference between the organizational identity perceptions of the teachers participating in the research and the variable of seniority. In his study, Ertürk (2018) found that there was a significant difference between teachers with 1-5 years, 6-10 years and 16 years and above according to the variable of seniority of teachers' perceptions of organizational identity. It stated that they have higher perceptions of identity. According to Ertürk's research, it can be said that as seniority increases, teachers' perceptions of organizational identity also increase.

It was determined that the teachers participating in the study did not show a significant difference between their perceptions of organizational identity and the variable of educational status. Çobanoğlu (2008) stated in his study that there is a significant difference between teachers who graduated with a Bachelors degree and teachers who graduated with a Masters degree, and that teachers who graduated with a Bachelors degree perceive the characteristics in the scale for the identity of the school more as identity than Master degree graduates.

There was no significant difference between the organizational identity perceptions of the teachers participating in the research and the variable of the level of education they work in, with support and belonging sub-dimensions. A significant relationship was found between the communication sub-dimension of the scale and the education level of the teachers. According to the research data, a significant difference was found between the teachers working at the preschool level and the primary school teachers, between the teachers working at the pre-school level and the teachers working at the secondary school level, and between the teachers working at the preschool level and the teachers working at the high school level. Accordingly, we can say that preschool teachers have higher communication perceptions than teachers working at primary, secondary and high school levels. In similar studies, Çobanoğlu (2008) and Akgül (2012) stated that teachers working at primary school level have higher organizational identity perceptions than branch teachers.

It was determined that there was no significant difference between the organizational identity perceptions of the teachers participating in the research and the type of institution variable.

The level of work effort of the teachers participating in the research was high with =3.95 as "I agree". It has been determined that there is no significant difference between the work effort of the teachers participating in the research and the variable of gender, seniority, education level, education level and the institution they are affiliated with.

In this study, it was determined that there was a high level of positive and significant relationship between teachers' perceptions of organizational identity and work effort. Considering the positive relationship between organizational identity perception and work effort, the high level of work effort perception may be effective in increasing teachers' perceptions of organizational identity. Therefore, it can be said that teachers' feeling themselves as an important and valuable employee of the school is related to the perception of organizational identity.

According to the research data, it has been determined that 11.9% of teachers' perceptions of organizational identity stem from work effort. Studies to determine which variables affect the remaining 88% are important for the identity perception that will be formed in organizations.

Qualitative research will contribute to the literature in order to determine the factors affecting the work effort of teachers and to increase the work effort.

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